

WORKING ON THE CONTENT AND TEXT OF AN ARTISTIC WORK IN PRIMARY SCHOOL READING CLASSES

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses about studying a number of methods of working on the content of a work of art in elementary reading lessons and the types and methods of working on the text of a work of art.

In a work of art, all its components (conceptual basis, composition, plot, pictorial means) are interconnected. The image develops in the work. New aspects of the image are revealed in connection with the plot of the work. These features require a comprehensive reading, perception, that is, synthesis, while working on the work. After reading the text from the beginning to the end, it is analyzed and the final conclusion is reached. Based on these, the artistic work is divided into the main stages for working on the text.

The main task of the first stage is to introduce the exact content of the work and its plot line, to determine the emotional impact of the work based on the overall perception of the text. The tasks and work content of the second stage are to determine the beginning of the cause and effect of the development of the plot, to determine the behavior of the participating persons and their main characteristics, to

reveal the composition of the work, to analyze the specific content of the work together with visual means, and to evaluate the behavior of the characters. The content of the work of the third stage consists of summarizing the important characteristics of the participating persons, comparing and evaluating the heroes, determining the direction of the work, evaluating the work of art as a source of knowledge of life and a work of art.

Before understanding the work of art, work on the text is carried out, each image in the text is worked on, the meaning of new words in it is explained. In order for students to understand the content of the work correctly, it is necessary to have a certain idea about life and a certain level of accurate knowledge about existence. Before understanding the work of art, work on the text is carried out, each image in the text is worked on, the meaning of new words in it is explained. In order for

students to understand the content of the work correctly, it is necessary to have a certain idea about life and a certain level of accurate knowledge about existence.

When perceiving the work, it is taken into account that the author reflects not only his opinion, but also his imagination. It is necessary to read it expressively in order for the students to have a clear and emotional perception of the work. In this case, preparatory exercises conducted before reading the work are important.

The tasks of preparatory work are as follows:

1. Enriching students' imaginations about the events depicted in the work, providing new information that affects the conscious perception of the text, creating conditions for students to be able to connect the facts described in the work of art with what they have observed in their lives.
2. To introduce the life of writers, to arouse interest in the author (writer, poet) and his work.
3. Preparing students for emotional perception of the work.
4. Explain the lexical meaning of the words unfamiliar to the students in the work and make a dictionary.

The teacher decides whether or not to conduct preparatory exercises before reading the work, taking into account the content of the work and the general level of the students.

In primary grades, the task of teaching correct, fast, conscious and expressive reading is carried out along with the formation of the ability to analyze the work and its text in students. The interrelationship between the formation of reading skills and working on the text determines how to approach the analysis of

the work. The methodical rule of the analysis of the work is to look at the content of the work in connection with its pictorial means of expression. Another basic rule is the comprehensive implementation of educational tasks in the process of working on the work. These rules determine the main direction of work on the work, and also help to determine the nature of the questions that will be asked to students in the process of analyzing the text.

The main direction of the analysis of the content of the text is to determine the specific theme of the work (events and plot development), its composition, morals and character traits of the participating persons, and the idea of the work.

In the experience of elementary school, it is appropriate to start the analysis of the work with questions and assignments such as "Who is the story told about in the work?", "Name the persons participating in the story."

The following types of work on the text are used in the analysis process.

1. Selective reading. In this case, the student reads the part of the text corresponding to the given task. The task is to clarify the theme of the work, determine the cause-and-effect relationship, reveal the artistic features of the work, and express one's personal attitude to the read text.

In selective reading, different difficulties are used at all stages of working on the text. Selective reading is an even more complex type of reading that requires comparing and summarizing the facts related to cause and effect from the text. In this, the student selects and reads material (sentences) from the text to confirm how a participant behaves and why he behaves

like that. Selective reading enables the formation of conscious and expressive reading skills along with the improvement of the ability to work on the text, the development of students' creative imagination, speech and thinking, therefore it is widely used. Selective reading is used when creating a text plan (finding a sentence that expresses its content in a text part, i.e. a point of the plan), describing the hero, and determining the idea of the work (reading to find the place that represents the idea).

One of the most common types of work in working on the content of the text is to answer the given question in one's own words. This type of text makes it possible to evaluate the persons participating in the development of students' ability to discuss what they have read, and to determine the events between the scenes described by the author and the idea of the work. The questions should be directed to a certain goal and should be in a certain consistency. When working on the text, both questions that require the retelling of the topic of the text and questions in the form of cause and effect are used. If the teacher intends to help the students to understand the idea of the work, the question will be in the form of cause and effect.

2. Teach students to ask questions about the text. With this work, good results are achieved when working on the text. In his works, K.D. Ushinsky emphasizes the importance of teaching students to ask questions and says, "If the teacher can ask the question correctly, half of the answer will be ready."

In order to teach students to consciously formulate questions, the teacher analyzes the questions that he has

created in the text or given in the textbook. Why is this or that question asked for analysis, who or what is it about, what words do the questions start with, which questions are more interesting and difficult? Uses questions like and teaches how to answer these questions using the text.

Secondly, the teacher teaches the students how to make a question based on the text, and before making a question, he explains that it is necessary to read the text carefully, show the participating persons (images), and separate the part where the question is made. At the initial stage of teaching questions, this exercise is done as a team and has an educational character. For this, a more convenient question is selected and explained why it is convenient and interesting, or, on the contrary, why it is uncomfortable. After that, he will be tasked with writing questions to the text. Creating a question requires students to familiarize themselves with the content of the work, develops the skill of conscious reading, and ensures activity in checking homework.

3. Description of the text. This method is of great importance in working on the text, it develops the creative abilities of students, and its correct use creates favorable conditions for students to clearly imagine the life scenes described by the writer in the work. The text is described in two ways.

1. Describe with words
2. Graphic representation.

Description with words is a complex type of work, in which a scene or an event in the text is required to be accurately recreated with the help of words. In order to describe in words, as well as graphically, the reader needs to know the text, the

place and situation of the incident, the appearance and character of the participants, and the precise choice of words. requires, it is one of the useful tools for developing students' speech.

The teacher can use the description for various purposes, to prepare for retelling as a basis for making a plan, to determine the circumstances of the incident. Depicting is also used as an independent task: the teacher instructs the students to describe a scene they like very well in words or graphics from a certain part of the text and to choose the author (author) word for it.

Before retelling the story, the students read the text to describe it with words, separate the relative completed parts, describe the scenes in order. This allows you to visualize what the writer wrote about. After that, lexical and syntactic preparation is carried out for retelling the text.

It is appropriate to start teaching the description of the text by comparing the picture given in the book with the part of the text corresponding to this picture. In this case, the students are convinced that the artist was able to show the characteristics of the character or nature described by the writer.

Describing with words should not be difficult to retell. For this, the author helps to analyze the text from the lexical syntactic point of view, to choose the right word when describing the scene.

During the analysis, the teacher draws students' attention to the words and phrases used by the author.

Graphic representation is done more often, for this students separate the part of the text to be depicted. They re-read

it carefully, absorb its content and draw a picture corresponding to it.

In the lesson, the students choose to study based on the pictures they draw. Screening is a more complex type of graphic representation than text. This is a creative work in which the pictures are combined with the text. For this, a series of pictures is created in a certain sequence, according to the development of the plot of the work. Screening is done in parts, frames are selected together with references and music.

Full, abbreviated, selective and creative retelling, as well as making a plan of the read story, article or fairy tale, helps to learn the visual means of the text content.

4. Creating a work plan. This work serves for a conscious and deep understanding of the content of the work. The plan helps students to distinguish the main idea in the text, determine the sequence of events, and understand the interconnection of text parts.

Working on the plan improves students' speech and thinking. They learn to divide the text into content-complete parts, to find the basis of each part and form it as a plan point in the form of a short and clear title. The simplest type of preparatory exercise is to find a suitable subtext content from the given headings.

It is even better if students can find the title of the small text themselves. When teaching such an exercise, the teacher emphasizes that the title expresses the main idea, analyzes the title found by the children and explains why this or that title is suitable or not suitable. The second type of preparatory work for making a plan is selective reading under the guidance of a teacher. Children read the text, finding the

answer to the question given by the teacher.

Planning is gradually made more difficult based on the principle of easy to complex and is carried out in a certain consistency from the 1st grade. Under the guidance of the teacher, choosing a title for the small text read by the students of the 1st grade according to the program of the mother tongue of the elementary grades, the text plan read in the 3rd grade first as a team, and then is taught to compose independently.

The simplest form of plan is a pictorial plan. For this purpose, children are first taught to choose the appropriate part of the text from the pictures given in the book and name it (put a title), then the text part is not given a ready-made picture, but the students describe it with their own words. The story is read and analyzed by parts, then students read the first part of the text. The teacher asks them how to draw, they answer. They draw pictures and name them, that is, they find a title for the text.

They read the second part of the text, describe it with words and name it. The teacher writes the headings on the board in the form of an outline. Pupils go from creating a pictorial plan to making a logical plan. Logical planning is taught in the following sequence.

1. The teacher selects a text divided into parts, prepares a plan and changes the position (order) of the points of the text plan and writes it on the left side of the board in the form of a title. Pupils read the first part of the text, choose the title corresponding to the content of this part from the board. The teacher writes it on the right side of the board, then the students

read the second part of the text and choose the corresponding title from the board. In this way, the plan of the text read on the board is formed.

2. In the process of analyzing parts of the text, under the guidance of the teacher, students determine the main idea in each part and find a title for it. The teacher writes the headings on the blackboard in the form of bullet points.

3. A text that is not divided into parts is selected, the headings are written on the board in the order of the text plan. Students are instructed to divide the text into parts using the given headings. They read the text, distinguish the part corresponding to the first title, and the next parts are marked in the same way.

4. The text that is not divided into parts is selected, the titles are written on the board in a mixed manner. Pupils are assigned to divide into the above parts. Students read the text, divide it into relative complete parts and choose the corresponding title from the board. The work continues in this way and the text plan is drawn up.

Students are gradually taught to divide the work into parts independently and find a title for each part, that is, to create a plan of the given text. To make a plan, you can use interrogative and indicative sentences, and in some cases, a noun phrase. Only one type of sentence should be used in each plan. All the points of the plan should be composed of a declarative sentence or an interrogative sentence. Thus, in the formation and development of the students' ability to work on the text, they focus on the content of the work and ways of doing it.

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